

Digital Literacy Culture in the Development of Student Character

Yasmin Aurellisa Wijaya

202410100110049

English Education, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, University of Muhammadiyah Malang

Email: aurellisayasmin@webmail.umm.ac.id

Abstract:

Digital literacy culture plays a crucial role in shaping student character by enhancing their ability to adapt to, recognize, and comprehend information in the rapidly evolving digital era. Digital literacy goes beyond reading and writing skills; it involves identifying, understanding, and applying information from increasingly diverse and complex digital platforms. According to UNESCO (2017), digital literacy culture helps students adapt to emerging technologies, there by strengthening character education by instilling values such as honesty, responsibility, discipline, and creativity essential for daily life and learning. Nugroho (2025) asserts that digital literacy is an effective pathway to reinforce student character in the face of challenges within the advanced Society 5.0 era, integrating technology with in social life. This study utilizes a case study method focusing on the implementation and observation of digital literacy culture in schools. Findings reveal that the application of digital literacy enhances students' of 4C skills (critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity), despite the still relatively low reading interest among students. Learning models such as service learning, project-based learning, problem-based learning, and the LOK-R model are integral to the structured implementation of digital literacy and character development. Nevertheless, challenges remain, including technological limitations, disparities in access, and gaps in teacher and student understanding. Support from educators, schools, families, and communities is fundamental for successful character development through digital literacy culture, enabling students to confidently and competently face future technological advancements.

Keywords: *Digital Literacy, Character Development, 4C Skills*

Introduction:

Learning in a school often has different visions and missions compared to other schools. One of the elements involved is the curriculum, which essentially includes criteria that teachers are expected to achieve. For instance, one of Indonesia's cultural practices, such as the culture of literacy, plays an important role in the digital era today. The *OECD* emphasizes that digital platforms are crucial in sustaining education continuity. The topic discussed here is the culture of digital literacy in the development of students' character, highlighting the potential of understanding digital literacy culture, which is highly relevant in the current digital era. According to *Nugroho (2025)*,

digital literacy culture can be an effective pathway to strengthen character education in the Society 5.0 era. This era is characterized by modern technology that allows easy and fast access to a vast amount of information through various digital media. Literacy, derived from the English word "*literacy*," means the ability to learn. Literacy skills are not limited to the ability to read and write.

According to *UNESCO (2017)*, the culture of digital literacy among students encompasses an individual's ability to adapt, understand, and become accustomed to digital environments. This includes the capacity for adaptation and habituation within students, aimed at broadening sustainable literacy over time. Digital literacy is crucial for enhancing both the quality of education and the holistic development of students' character. Culture itself carries a specific meaning as a pattern that embraces habits and behaviors. Essentially, these patterns develop progressively within society, including in digital contexts. *UNESCO* defines digital literacy as the ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate, and effectively use information in various digital formats.

UNESCO (2017) revealed that Indonesia ranks 60th out of 61 countries with one of the lowest literacy rates in the world. Therefore, character building in students is implemented as a process to instill moral values, ethics, and positive attitudes within them. This character development must include elements such as honesty, responsibility, discipline, and creativity, which should be reflected in students' daily behavior both at school and in the community. Thus, this development can strengthen students' sense of responsibility and creativity in facing the abundance of digital information. However, there are still many challenges to overcome, such as limited technology, varying levels of teacher understanding, and disparities in access across regions. Digital literacy is a critical aspect embedded within student learning.

This aims to provide ample freedom in understanding the material and broader learning. Therefore, reading skills in digital literacy must be a primary focus in education (*Setiawan, 2021*). Digital literacy can be understood as the way of engaging attention, thinking, and skills with digital devices for the purpose of seeking knowledge or understanding through digital media (*Wardatussururi, 2025*). In this context, the *Ministry of Education and Culture Regulation No. 23 of 2017 on Strengthening Character Education (PPK)* also emphasizes the importance of developing critical, creative, and responsible attitudes in the use of technology. These are integral parts of shaping students' character in the digital world. However, as we know, the implementation of digital literacy education in Indonesia is not yet fully aligned with expectations, especially when compared to developed countries such as Singapore and Malaysia. These countries have made significant progress in curriculum implementation, which is widely recognized. They possess more advanced technological infrastructure, strong curriculum policy support, and comprehensive digital literacy programs integrated throughout their education systems.

The characteristics of students in digital literacy learning in Indonesia tend to be diverse due to differences in technology access and digital skills. Students are capable of filtering the vast amount of information and knowledge they acquire. *Sriyanto (2021)* states that student character plays a role in developing the 4C skills (*Critical thinking, Communication, Collaboration, and Creativity*). Overall, these studies show that digital

literacy not only helps students master technology but also enhances their critical thinking abilities, despite challenges in its implementation (Arif Fadlullah et al., 2024). One major challenge is the difficulty in distinguishing accurate understanding of digital technology information. The Merdeka Curriculum includes digital literacy learning that provides space for students to develop critical, creative, and collaborative thinking skills. This is reflected in their habits, such as rarely visiting the library except when assigned tasks. To achieve advanced digital literacy education, improvements in technological facilities, teacher training, and collaboration among schools, families, and communities are necessary.

It is evident that students' reading interest is very low due to a lack of awareness about reading within themselves (Wardatussururi, 2025). Paul & Elder (2006) emphasize the importance of integrating critical thinking instruction into the curriculum at all educational levels (Warastuti et al., 2025). Teachers need to be more proactive in encouraging and fostering students' low reading interest until they develop awareness themselves. Therefore, the implementation of digital literacy and character development in students must be improved, as this can trigger the progress of Indonesia's desired outcomes. This will help Indonesia catch up with developed countries that have successfully achieved digital literacy in shaping students' character more optimally. An example of what should be present in digital literacy learning is that students become accustomed to reading information from various platforms and are able to filter out negative content from digital information. Thus, this approach can already enhance students' digital literacy skills.

Statement Problem:

Digital literacy culture plays a significant role in the development of students' character, involving the instillation of values such as honesty, responsibility, discipline, socialization, and creativity. In this context, it is crucial to understand how digital literacy culture can be properly and effectively implemented in shaping students' character. Furthermore, in its application in Indonesia, digital literacy culture faces various challenges, including limited access to technology, low digital understanding among teachers, communities, and students, as well as the widespread dissemination of negative misinformation. Therefore, the roles of school principals, teachers, families, and the community are essential in supporting the strengthening of students' character. This collaborative effort can swiftly achieve the targeted improvement in the 4C competencies (*Critical thinking, Communication, Collaboration, Creativity*), which are vital for advancing students' character development in line with the progressing digital technology era.

Learning Methods:

A learning model is a teaching plan that pays attention to a specific learning pattern. This aligns with Briggs' definition, which describes a model as "a set of procedures arranged sequentially to realize a learning process." There are several learning models used in education today. Bem and Erikson, as cited in Komalasari, implement learning by relating the taught material to real-world situations experienced

by students. Some examples include service learning, project-based learning, problem-based learning, and the LOK-R learning model. These models, along with practical examples, are explained below.

- Learning Model:

- a. *Service Learning:*

- This model provides to students involves the use of digital technology applications that are easy and practical. In this process, students learn to understand real-world problems within a program by see for solutions with the aid of technology. For example, students conduct digital literacy training for the surrounding community.

- b. *Project-Based Learning:*

- This learning model is based on principles and concepts that assign tasks to students. It requires students to create a real project where they must apply digital literacy skills to complete it. For example, students may develop an educational podcast project about digital literacy ethics. In doing so, students need to search for relevant information.

- c. *Problem-Based Learning:*

- This learning approach involves students in problem-solving by applying various concepts and personal skills, including data collection and information synthesis. The final outcome requires students to present the problems they have identified. Using technology and digital information sources, students develop critical thinking skills and work effectively. For example, students may find an article containing information about online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. The article highlights that many people agree that frequent online learning helps students better understand and master the culture of digital literacy. Students are then expected to solve this problem and produce accurate results.

- d. *LOK-R Learning Model:*

- The LOK-R learning model is a new instructional approach developed in 2018 by Nuansa Bayu Segara, E. Maryani, N. Supriatna, and M. Ruhimat. The LOK-R model is implemented in stages, where students are expected to begin learning activities by observing and reading. In the next stage, students are guided by the teacher to develop new ideas and skills through various learning tasks. For example, students watch a video from YouTube and read an online article, then they form groups to present problems based on the video and article.

Learning Theories:

1. Enactive Learning Theory:

Jerome S. Bruner provides significant insights into human cognitive development, explaining how people learn, acquire knowledge, and transform it. Some students may become accustomed to the learning process of literacy, especially in the context of digital use. This implementation can trigger various stages to carry out learning directly. The actions taken allow learners to extract important information during literacy activities. Students will directly experience the content they read. In this digital literacy theory, the understanding they gain must come from actively and habitually reading a wide range of informational texts. Next, students act by identifying the main idea or key points contained in the texts they have read. By exploring this information, students acquire new knowledge that is indirectly embedded in the information discovered (Vita & Zainal, 2020).

2. Think, Talk, and Write Theory:

In the Think, Talk, and Write stage, according to Deporter (2001), this is a learning process where students first learn individually by understanding the problems within informational texts. Then, students are actively involved in group discussions, and the process concludes with students writing a summary of their learning individually, following the given learning format and instructions. After reading the information, students make notes of the main ideas and outcomes from their reading. They are required to interact with their peers, and individually, the teacher will ask them about their notes on the information or issues. In the final stage, the teacher observes and assesses the extent of students' digital literacy development and character growth through their interactions with peers and the teacher.

3. Inquiry Theory:

Inquiry theory involves actions where students are given broad opportunities to directly share information. They are encouraged to ask specific questions, seek precise answers, and develop their own understanding through deep learning experiences. This approach supports students' motor skills development because they gradually search, create, and produce broader outcomes. The development of critical thinking focuses more specifically and relevantly on students' character development needs. As explained by Handayani (2020), the Inquiry approach teaches students to be more critical and expansive in processing the information they receive, encouraging them to continuously question and evaluate facts. Therefore, implementing the Inquiry stage can trigger more positive impacts on critical thinking and character development in students.

Research Methodology:

In the learning of digital literacy culture for student character development, a case study method is used, focusing on application and in-depth observation. The observation aims to determine whether students are able to apply and habituate digital literacy culture in the school or classroom environment. For the program to run smoothly, clarity and seamless implementation are essential, including adequate facilities and technology to support the program effectively. The learning process involves theories that stimulate various stages through which students can gain direct understanding. Following this, students enter the next phase of learning using the Think, Talk, Write method. In this phase, students first read the entire text, then note the main ideas they find, and finally discuss them by talking with their peers or teachers. After completing these steps, students undergo a final action aimed at developing critical thinking. This step requires students to focus more specifically and relevantly on applying the character values they gain from the digital literacy culture program.

Result and Discussion:

No.	Syntax:	Material:	Student Activities:
1.	Service Learning.	Basic digital literacy to help students use digital technology safety.	Students design a training program in which safe use of digital technology is applied as a form of character implementation.
2.	Project Based Learning (PjBL).	Principles of using social media and positive digital information activities.	Students create a project (podcast or video) that provides education about ethical digital technology use, then publish it online.
3.	Problem Based Learning (PBL).	Distinguishing factual news from hoaxes in digital media.	Students search for examples of online news, analyze the information from these sources, and then present the result of their analysis in class.
4.	LOK-R Learning Model.	Reading and analyzing digital videos or articles in general.	Students watch an educational video, read a related article, take notes on the main ideas, then discuss and present them in groups.
5.	Think, Talk, Write in Digital Literacy.	Preparing summaries and character reflection from	Students read a digital article, understand the key

		digital technology information.	information, then write a final summary and present it.
--	--	---------------------------------	---

Digital literacy implementation plays an important role in developing students' character. It involves internalizing and habituating digital literacy so that students can continuously expand their digital literacy practices. In this context, digital literacy contributes to enhancing students' knowledge by encouraging them to read various types of information through digital technologies. This internalization also helps improve individuals' understanding when drawing conclusions from the information they obtain, while character growth supports the development of students' moral values and attitudes. Digital literacy further shapes students to be active in developing the 4C skills (Critical thinking, Communication, Collaboration, and Creativity). This implementation becomes a crucial form of assessment to ensure that students not only receive and read information, but also understand and apply it in real situations. Students' participation during this process allows them to practise actively and purposefully, which leads to a higher level of learning goals and indicates significant improvement in their understanding and skills in technology and digital literacy. In addition, the important roles of teachers, schools, and parents strengthen the guidance needed for student character development, helping to prevent negative impacts of digital technology. These efforts aim to enhance digital understanding and literacy so that students are not left behind and are better prepared to face future developments in digital technology.

Conclusion:

The discussion of research findings on digital literacy culture in developing students' character shows that improvements in students' participation in digital literacy programs are still in the development stage. Digital literacy culture must be further strengthened through effective character education. The abilities achieved by students currently include several aspects such as adapting, understanding, and habituating the use of digital literacy. If not implemented properly, the condition of low reading interest may persist. This situation can affect students' ability to comprehend reading materials and reduce their active participation in literacy activities. Nevertheless, various challenges still need to be addressed, such as limited technology, teachers' level of understanding, and unequal access to technology across regions. Optimizing character formation in students can help Indonesia catch up in achieving more advanced digital literacy. To ensure that digital literacy can be implemented smoothly and appropriately, several strategies are needed, such as the use of digital media (platforms, articles, websites), projector-based learning, and learning models including *service learning*, *project-based learning*, *problem-based learning*, and *the LOK-R model*. The development of critical thinking in students' character aims to help them stay more focused, directed, and relevant. This indicates a significant increase in students' understanding and skills in the fields of technology and digital literacy (Nailatur Rizkiyah, 2025).

References:

Anwar, A. (2022). Media Sosial Sebagai Inovasi Pada Model PjBL Dalam Implementasi

Kurikulum Merdeka. *Inovasi Kurikulum*, 19(2), 239-250.

Arif Fadlullah, Amelia Manda Sari, Wahdana, Farhan Muhammad Nabil, Devi Sarmilah Chomariah, Widya Ambarwati, & Muhammad Irfan. (2024). Edukasi Teknologi dan Literasi Digital kepada Siswa SMP Negeri 12 Tarakan. *JURPIKAT (Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat)*, 5(2), 509-523. <https://doi.org/10.37339/jurpikat.v5i2.1574>

Dewi, F. (2015). Proyek Buku Digital: Upaya Peningkatan Keterampilan Abad 21 Calon Guru Sekolah Dasar Melalui Model Pembelajaran Berbasis Proyek. *Metodik Didaktik*, 9(2), 1 – 15.

Dhesita, S. J. (2022). Analisis Penerapan Model Pembelajaran LOK-R Terhadap Kemampuan Literasi Siswa dalam Pembelajaran Sejarah. *Jurnal Ilmiah WUNY*, 4(2), 1-12.

Fitriana, D., & Maro, R. K. (2018). Teaching vocabulary through snake and ladder board game in the tenth grade of SMA Muhammadiyah 1 Malang. *Celtic: A Journal of Culture, English Language Teaching, Literature and Linguistics*, 3(1), 82-93.

Literasi, I., Pada, D., Ipas, P., Febiola, D., Studi, P., Guru, P., Ibtidaiyah, M., & Tarbiyah, F. (2025). Implementasi literasi digital pada pembelajaran ipas kelas v sd negeri 17 rejang lebong.

Maro, R. K. (2016). Strategi Pembelajaran K-13 Melatih Critical Thinking. *J. Chem. Inf. Model*, 53(9), 1689-1699.

Maro, R. K., & Nurbatra, L. H. (2013). Building Critical Thinking Behavior of Middle School Students through Project Based Learning. In *The 1st ELITE Conference* (pp. 582-594).

Nazilatur Rizkiyah. (2025). Implementasi Pembelajaran Berbasis Literasi Digital dalam Jurnal Ilmiah Literasi Indonesia. *Jurnal Ilmiah Literasi Indonesia*, 1(1), 29 – 35.

Neti Nurhandayani, Skripsi: "Pengaruh Model Pembelajaran Problem Based Learning (PBL) Terhadap Hasil Belajar Tematik Peserta Didik Kelas V SDN" (Lampung: Keguruan dan Ilmu Pendidikan Universitas Lampung Bandar Lampung, 2022), hal. 16-17.

Nurrohmah, Fitri. 2015. Penerapan Model Pembelajaran Think Talk Write Terhadap Hasil Belajar Siswa dan Aktivitas Belajar Peserta Didik Pada Kompetensi Dasar Bipolar Junction Transistor Kelas X-TAV di SMKN 1 Nganjuk. Skripsi. Tidak Diterbitkan. Fakultas Teknik. Universitas Negeri Surabaya: Surabaya.

Restu, N. K., Sutini, A., & Dewi, D. A. (2023). Pengaruh media wordwall sebagai instrumen penilaian PPKn SD terhadap kemampuan literasi digital dan kreatifitas guru dalam mengajar. *COLLASE (Creative of Learning Students Elementary Education)*. 06(01), 94 – 101.

Sriyanto, B. (2021). Meningkatkan Keterampilan 4C Dengan Literasi Digital di SMP Negeri 1 Sidoharjo. *Jurnal Didaktika Pendidikan Dasar*, 5(1), 125-142.

Warastuti, W., Prayitno, H.J., & Rahmawati, L. E. (2025). Penerapan Literasi Digital dalam Membangun Kemampuan Berpikir Kritis Siswa di Sekolah Dasar. *Cetta: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*, 8(2), 350-365. <https://doi.org/10.37329/cetta.v8i2.4143>

Wardatussururi, Y. (2025). STRATEGI GURU DALAM MENINGKATKAN MINAT BACA

*SISWA DI MI YAQIN 3 KWANG RUNDUN DESA KWANG RUNDUN Teachers
' Strategies in Increasing Students ' Reading Interest at MI Yaqin 3 Kwang
Rundun Kwang Rundun Village , Jerowaru District. 3(2), 125-136.*